

INFLUENCE OF ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE AND TEACHER COMPETENCE ON SUCCESSFUL CHANGE THROUGH COMMITMENT TO CHANGE

ZAENUDIN¹, IKA NURUL QAMARI² and SRI HANDARI WAHYUNINGSIH³

^{1,2,3}Muhammadiyah University of Yogyakarta, Indonesia. Email: ¹zaenudinrefo@gmail.com

Abstract

The school as an organization, will be largely determined by the teacher to be able to achieve progress. Teacher as the main part as human resources, has a very important role in advancing the school. Teachers have several roles that must be raised during teaching and learning activities. In addition to teachers, teacher performance also greatly determines the success of school activities. Teacher performance is strongly influenced by the quality of competence and commitment to change following the developments that occur. The research method chosen in this study is the SLR (Systematic Literature Review) method. Data collection is carried out by documenting and reviewing all articles related to the application of the Influence of Organizational Culture and Teacher Competence on Successful Change through Change Commitments published in the 2012-2020 period. The articles used in this study were 27 accredited international journal articles obtained from the Google Scholar database. Based on this research, it was found that there is a positive relationship between organizational culture and teacher competence towards successful change through a commitment to change.

Keywords: Organizational culture, teacher competence, successful change, commitment to change

A. INTRODUCTION

1. Basic Concepts of Change

Organizational readiness to change is very important in facing the changing times. Revolution 4.0 brought significant changes in all walks of life, including the field of education. Digitization on multiple fronts is causing the process for innovation to get shorter. This is a challenge in itself, especially for sectors that are still working traditionally.

Where in antiquity innovation was usually born from competitive environmental challenges and today it comes from other sectors. Sectors that are still working traditionally, including education, must be agile in keeping pace with the development of the times and technology. The field of education must be able to innovate. Change is an integral part of the manager's work. Organizational change is a variety of changes that occur in the human resources (HR), structure or technology of an organization. The characteristics of the changes are:

- a) There is a high level of diversity
- b) The existence of uncertainty and unpredictability
- c) Creating opportunities and challenges

The urge to change comes from external and internal impulses. External impetus comes from market forces, government laws and policies, technology, labor market and economic change while the impulses that come from internal are changes in organizational strategy, changes in

labor, new equipment and technologies and worker behavior. Changes within the organization require a catalyst. People who are able to be catalysts and are responsible for the process of change as agents of change. Managers are change agents in the organization. Changes can be implemented by managers who act as internal entrepreneurs. However, change agents can also come from non-managers who specialize in handling changes, for example change specialists from the human resources department or outside consultants are experts in the implementation of changes. Often organizations hire outside consultants to provide advice in processing changes because they are more objective and have no vested interest. However, outside consultants often do not understand the character of the organization very well. The process of change is viewed from two different views, namely the calm waters methaphor and the white-water rapids methaphor.

Lewin stated that successful changes can be planned and require unfreezing of the status quo, changing to a new state (changing) and refreezing a new state so that a more permanent status quo is considered a balanced state and to move away from this condition requires disbursement. Therefore, it takes the driving force to change. After the disbursement is completed, the changes themselves can be implemented. However, simply starting a change does not guarantee that the change will last. The new situation must be frozen again so that the situation can be maintained forever. If this step is not taken, it is likely that the change will not last long and return to its original state.

Low and unpredictable environmental stability requires a manager and organization that is able to adapt continuously so that it can survive. This metaphor fits into a situation of changing a highly dynamic environment dominated by information, ideas and knowledge. Therefore, it is necessary to be flexible and quick to respond to the changes that occur.

2. Managing Changes

a. Changes in Structure, Technology and Human Resources

The choice of change in the organization is categorized into three groups, namely changes in structure, technology and human resources

1) Structure Changes

Changes that occur in the design and structure of the organization or its structural components. The responsibility of organizing the manager includes such activities as choosing a formal organizational design, allocating authority, and determining the degree of formalization. Basically, the structure changes based on work specialization, departmentalization, chain of command, range of control, centralization and decentralization and formalization. Managers can change one or two components within the structure

2) Technology Changes

Managers can also change the technology used to convert inputs into outputs. Factors of competition or new innovations often require organizations to change technology. Technological changes are related to adopting new technologies or methods that replace old equipment such as automation and computerization.

3) HR changes

For more than 30 years, research has been conducted that examines individuals and organizations to work together more effectively. Basically, organizational development focuses on changing human resources and changing work behavior.

3. Studies in Managing Change

Contemporary studies related to change are organizational culture change, continuous quality improvement versus reengineering, and stress management in employees.

a. Organizational Culture Change

Culture is naturally resistant to change. Cultural formation takes a long time and once it is formed, the culture tends to be deeply rooted in the organization. Strong cultures are very immune to change. However, cultural changes can occur if the following conditions are encountered:

- 1) A very dramatic crisis
- 2) Leadership change
- 3) Young, flexible and small organization
- 4) Weak organizational culture Various ways to change culture, namely:
- 5) Carrying out cultural analysis to identify cultural elements necessary for the existence of change
- 6) Make an explanation to workers that the organization that survives is legitimized if change does not occur
- 7) New leadership with a new vision
- 8) Reorganization initiation
- 9) Introducing new histories and rituals to develop a new vision
- 10) Changing the selection and socialization process, evaluation and new reward system to support new values

b. Continuous Quality Improvement Program versus Reengineering Process

The desired level of product quality requires a change in the way people work. Managers can make changes using ongoing quality programs or they can also be reengineered. The quality improvement program that continues according to the first point of view (the calm water metaphors).

Organizations should always look for ways to improve current performance. The focus of the activity is towards individuals who must participate in decision making. Meanwhile, the rekayas aulang corresponds to the second view (white water-rapids metaphor). The reengineering process is a process of dramatic and radical work change. This process focuses on quantum change and eliminates old ways of working.

c. Handling Stress in Employees

For some employees, change can cause stress. The dynamic and erratic environment has given rise to overworked and overly tense employees. Stress is a physical and psychological stress that is felt when facing excessive demand, limitations or opportunities associated with interests and uncertainty the causes of stress can be found in problems related to the organization or personal factors that arise from the employee's personal life.

The symptoms of stress are grouped into three, namely psychological, behavioral and physical. Symptoms that are less significant in managing stress are physical consequences. Symptoms that significantly affect the work of employees are psychological and behavioral symptoms.

Symptoms of stress in organizations can be reduced by:

- 1) Better labor selection
- 2) Customize the work
- 3) Using realistic interviews to reduce ambiguity
- 4) Improving organizational communication
- 5) Develop a performance planning program
- 6) Redesigning the job
- 7) Providing counseling programs
- 8) Offers time planning management assistance
- 9) Better sponsorship programs

Organizational changes do not have a significant effect if the change in strategy also does not change. Change is not only the responsibility of the top manager but also of all elements in the organization. However, engagement at all levels of management cannot always change the way things are supposed to work. Changes in the organization can be made by:

- 1) Embracing change so that organizations are able to change
- 2) Make a simple explanation that the change is indispensable for the sustainability of the organization
- 3) Continuous and honest communication
- 4) Encourage worker participation so that they are more loyal
- 5) Awakening workers' enthusiasm for flexibility
- 6) Reducing people who are resistant and unwilling to change The characteristics of organizational change are:
- 7) The interrelationship between the present and the future
- 8) Making life perspective learning
- 9) Actively support and awaken the spirit to change.
- 10) Convincing different teams
- 11) Encouraging unconventional people (mavericks).

12) Supporting new breakthroughs

13) Technology integration

14) Building and deepening trust

d. Generating Innovation

Innovation is the screening / change of the outcomes of the creative process into more useful products, services and work methods. The absolute requirement for novation is creativity. Creativity is the ability to combine ideas in a unique way or create something different.

B. LITERATURE REVIEW

a. The Influence of Organizational Culture on Commitment to Change

There are many definitions in the literature for what constitutes organizational culture. According to some, "the way we do things here" is the most popular definition (Lundy & Cowling, 1996). Cultural norms in organizations are discussed in this study, and they are defined as values and beliefs that are deeply ingrained in (often subconscious) organizations. A distinctive feature of an organization is a manifestation of the culture of that organization. A set of fundamental assumptions that have been proven in the past and present are accepted by the organization as a whole. In other words, this assumption is maintained as the correct way to do something or to understand problems in the company (which manifests itself in attitudes and behaviors). Organizational culture includes routine behaviors, norms, values, philosophies, rules of the game, and feelings (Hellriegel et al., 1998; Smit & Cronje, 1992 in Martins, 2003). Organizational culture has a significant impact on change because it often involves shifts in core values and assumptions (Smit & Cronje, 1997). It is difficult for management to change organizational culture because it has a relatively stable set of characteristics. People's beliefs, values, and attitudes are difficult to change (Armstrong, 1995; Hellriegel et al., 1998; Robbins, 1996). Whether or not culture can be changed is a hotly debated topic in academic circles.

The following are counter-arguments against cultural change:

1. Culture is a vague concept that is difficult to describe, control, or change.
2. Organizational culture change can be difficult due to ingrained cultural values and a desire to retain what has worked in the past.
3. This is impractical due to the difficulty of the technique, the scarcity of skills, and the length of time it takes to fully understand the new culture.
4. Fear is kept away by culture, which helps people get through difficult times. By providing stability and continuity and thus preventing people from changing cultures, culture can achieve this goal (Ivancevich & Matteson, 1993; Sempene et al., 2002).

Those who believe in the possibility of cultural transformation say it will take an average of five to ten years (Hellriegel et al., 1998; Newstrom & Davis, 1997). There are a number of

conditions that must be met for cultural change to occur, such as crisis situations (such as dramatic technological breakthroughs), new leaders (such as those with a different set of values), and young organizations. (Culture is not deeply embedded), and weak culture (culture that is not supported by all employees) (Coffey et al., 1994; Robbins, 1996).

For Robbins (1997), a general shift has been towards a more flexible and responsive organizational culture that focuses more on customer service, quality, and responsiveness. According to Harvey and Brown (2001), rapid environmental changes

b. The influence of organizational culture on successful change

According to Renae A. Jones (2020), in her research found the fact that at the time of implementation, employees who had a positive impression of the values of human relations in their division reported a higher level of readiness for change, which in turn, predicted the use of the system. In addition, the relationship between the reshaping of capabilities and the use of systems is mediated by readiness for change. The results of the analysis also show that, after implementation, employee satisfaction with system accuracy, user-friendliness, and formatting functions correlates positively with their preimplementation readiness to change. These findings are discussed in relation to their theoretical contribution to the literature of readiness for change, and in relation to the practical importance of developing a positive attitude of change among employees if the change initiative is to be successful.

c. The effect of teacher competence on change commitment

Teachers are one of the key elements in education, especially in schools. All other components, ranging from curriculum, facilities, infrastructure, costs, and so on will not have a significant effect, if the essence of learning, namely the interaction between teachers and students, is not qualified (Bahiroh et al., 2020). In fact, there is growing public awareness that without teachers, there is no formal education. There is no quality education without the presence of a sufficient number of professional teachers. The importance of teachers in transforming educational inputs has led many experts to state that there will be no change or improvement in the quality of schools without changes and improvements in the quality of teachers. Bryan J Weiner (2009) in his research explains that treating organizational readiness as a shared psychological state in which members of the organization feel committed to implementing organizational change and are confident in their collective ability to do so.

This way of thinking about organizational readiness is best suited for examining organizational changes in which changes in collective behavior are necessary to implement changes effectively and, in some cases, for changes to generate anticipated benefits. Theory testing will require further development of measurements and careful sampling decisions. This theory offers a means to reconcile the structural and psychological views of organizational readiness found in the literature. Further, the theory suggests the possibility that the strategies recommended by change management experts are the same end.

David Desplaces in his research says a comprehensive (albeit incomplete) approach to individual readiness for change and studies and predecessors explores the relationship

between macro- and micro-levels of change, i.e., objective and subjective work arrangements, and proposes meaningful measures in an effort to relate them to individuals. Readiness to change. This model offers a potentially useful way to guide and evaluate an individual's readiness to change in context.

This echoes the assertion of Pettigrew and colleagues (2001) that context and action are inseparable and that the study of change regarding individual readiness should explore how the contexts, contents, and processes of change along with their interconnections over time affect an individual's readiness for change. Therefore, future research should examine the impact that organizing characteristics have on change efforts, including developing reliable and objective measures that are psychometrically sound for measuring the variables defined in our model.

In addition, future studies should seek to understand how contextual variables relate to individual processes of change, such as self-efficacy, motivation to change, and internal dispositional variables, such as tolerance to ambiguity, internal locus of control, construction of dispositions of readiness for change. Furthermore, group norms and organizational cultural values that support or inhibit change need to be examined in relation to their influence on the readiness of individuals to change attitudes in an effort to seek a balance between change and rejection of it (Leana & Barry, 2000).

Finally, future work should test the proposed model in full including testing the relationship between an individual's readiness to change and newly adopted behaviors to assess the role of an individual's readiness to change in determining newly adopted behaviors including the direct and indirect role of self-efficacy on that relationship and the impact of the change context on overall change efforts.

C. METHODS

1. Search Methodology

The literature of this review was written using a search strategy focused on emerald-based international journals. Organizational culture, dedication, teacher performance, motivation at work, and teacher credentials are some of the search terms used.

2. Admission Standards

The following criteria are used to select the literature review we analyze: Research on Teacher Certification and Competence, and articles should be included in the Scopus database.

3. Exclusion Criteria

No publications yet. An exclusive article, first of its kind with an ingenious title and summary of all rated publications. Articles whose titles do not correspond to the search topic.

D. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

a. The Relationship between Organizational Culture and Commitment to Change

Although there is little empirical evidence that there is a strong link between organizational culture and engagement, it has been suggested that organizational culture characteristics, such as organizational values and beliefs, are related to organizational engagement and performance (Harrison, 1972; Peters and Waterman, 1982; Trice and Beyer, 1993). Furthermore, it has been suggested that bureaucratic work practices often lead to the rejection of employee involvement, whereas supportive work environments can lead to increased employee engagement and engagement (Brewer, 1993; Kratina, 1990).

b. The relationship between organizational culture and successful change

In the current context, it is difficult to overestimate the role of organizational culture. Developing a strong and strategically important culture in the early stages of the company's existence is very important. Culture, along with governance and organizational structure, is key to subsequent performance (Baron, Hannan, & Burton, 2001) and leads to success (Ouchi, 1981). According to Morente, Fers & izlavský (2017) argue that the close relationship between organization, culture and innovation is essential for survival. Providing a culture that is not easy to replicate can be the basis for creating a sustainable competitive advantage (SCA) (Rothaermel, 2015) that translates into financial results (Barney, 1986).

c. The relationship between teacher competence and change commitment

According to Bibi (2005), teacher competence is defined as the strength, expertise, or potential that a teacher has to carry out his duties successfully, and stability that does not change from one situation to another every time the teacher teaches. Means quality. Teacher competence is the ability of a teacher to teach effectively (De-Ketele, 1996). Deakin (2008) describes teacher competence as a combination of knowledge, diverse skills, understanding, values, and attitudes that lead to successful problem-solving actions. Rychen and Salganick (2003) describe competence as the ability to perform complex actions with ease, precision, and flexibility. Teacher competence is very important in the educational context. Selvi (2010) explains that teacher competence influences grades, behavior, communication, goals and education to support curriculum and professional development. Fafuwa (1974) found that quality education cannot be achieved without qualified and effective teachers.

Competence looks at the success of teachers and distinguishes between those who succeed in the relevant profession and those who do not. The Ministry of Education and Culture (2009) published 10 professional standards of teacher quality. The criteria include subject knowledge, human growth and student development, knowledge of Islamic ethical values, learning plans and strategies, student assessment, learning environment, effective communication, collaboration and partnership, and continuous learning. Professional Development, Ethics and Code of Ethics. English as a second/foreign language. Teachers must be able to understand subject knowledge, learning plans and strategies, student assessment, learning environment, and effective communication (NPSTP, 2009).

d. The relationship between teacher competence and successful change

The study of pedagogical skills in teacher education programs can lead to the improvement of pedagogical skills of teachers. To improve the quality of teacher education, it is important to increase the capacity and commitment of teachers (National Board of Education, 1998). This research will be very useful for teacher training programs. According to Jumani (2007), teacher assessment leads to the development of enduring teaching skills. Evaluating teacher effectiveness leads to efforts to correct identified weaknesses by improving teacher competence.

This research will also provide teachers with an understanding of the concept of competence and professional skills of teachers, which are very important for teaching. In this way, he can become an effective teacher by improving student learning. According to Rivikin, Hanushek and Cain (2005), teacher competence has a great influence on student learning outcomes. According to Manning and Patterson (2005), a qualified teacher without a commitment to his profession may not improve the quality of education. This research will help develop an understanding of the importance and relationship of teacher competence and their commitment to the teacher profession. Public institutions lack satisfied and dedicated teachers.

Teachers who are dissatisfied and uncommitted are incapable of trying to shape the future of the nation. When these teachers are satisfied and committed to their profession, they will achieve good results. Gamoran (2003) illustrates that through professional development opportunities we can increase the professional commitment of teachers. The study will help in this. According to Gupta and Mir (2013), highly qualified teachers have a higher level of job satisfaction than less qualified teachers.

e. The relationship between commitment to change and successful change

According to Yah (2014) describes three types of organizational commitment: affective (identification), continuity (engagement), and prescriptive (loyalty). Affective focuses on the emotions of employees and attachment to the organization. Building sustainably is the second part that involves realizing the very high costs of leaving the organization. Furthermore, it consists in the willingness of nurses to exceed hospital expectations, even if it requires additional work.

Normative attachment to the organization is determined by the nurse's sense of obligation and commitment to the organization and their willingness to leave. This type of engagement encourages caregivers to be optimistic about their willingness to change.

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